

IMPACT OF GOLD EXTRACTION IN THE SOYUDLU GOLD DEPOSIT LOCATED IN THE EASTERN ZANGAZUR BORDER AREA WITH ARMENIA ON WATER RESOURCES*Shirinova N.**University of Architecture and Construction of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Azerbaijan,
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Head of Laboratory, PhD in Physics***Abstract**

In the context of the socio-economic development of the regions of Azerbaijan, the strategy of using mineral resources (especially gold) occupies an important place. After liberation from occupation, it was considered expedient to form the Lachin, Jabrayil, Gubadli, Zangilan and Kalbajar regions as a single economic region under the name of East Zangezur. The length of the Tartarchay, the most important among the rivers flowing from the Soyudlu bed, is approximately 200 km, and the water basin is 2650 km². Pollutants entering this river damage aquatic ecosystems, cause mass extinction of fish and other living creatures, make the waters of these rivers completely unsuitable for drinking and irrigation purposes, and pose a risk to the health of the local population. In the present work, the ecological damage caused by gold mining activities to the ecosystem, especially to water sources, is analyzed in detail.

Keywords: Eastern Zangezur, Soyudlu (Zod) deposit, ore mining industry, gold deposits, cyanide, mercury, water resources, environmental pollution, epidemiological situation.

Introduction

With the successful implementation of state programs for the socio-economic development of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan, sustainable and balanced development of cities and regions of our country has been ensured, and the appearance of our cities, villages and settlements has changed radically. The well-being of the population in the regions has increased, infrastructure provision and economic potential have increased, the quality of state services provided to the population, and the business and investment environment have improved. Currently, measures are being taken to restore the territories liberated from occupation, create necessary infrastructure, ensure their future development, and return the population to their native lands. This requires the effective use of the natural resources, tourism opportunities and rich economic potential of these territories, and the implementation of all work intended to ensure the necessary level of development on the basis of a single program, and the review of the division of the liberated territories into economic regions.

The Zangezur plateau, which covers a large area from Kalbajar and Lachin to Nakhchivan, is located in the eastern part of the Zangezur plateau, covering a large area from Nakhchivan to Nakhchivan, the Zangezur mountain range is located in the same geographical area, on the border with Armenia, and is part of the Zangezur district, which was established in 1981, and their traditional historical-cultural, socio-economic connections necessitated the unification of Lachin, Jabrayil, Gubadli, Zangilan and Kalbajar districts into a single economic region [1].

The increase in demand for gold, copper and other precious metals in the world market has further increased interest in the mining industry in the Republic of Armenia since 2001. Although large investments

have been made for the development of the mining industry, this has ultimately led to sharp changes in the ecological situation in a negative direction. This is seriously reflected in the current state of the ecological situation in the regions of countries where the mining industry is developed. In particular, the location of some mines near water resources has led to environmental pollution with toxic substances [10].

According to statistical data, water samples have been taken from rivers located in the cities of Agarak, Kapan, and Kacharan in Armenia since 2018. The results showed that the amount of toxic substances and heavy metals (molybdenum, copper, mercury, etc.) in the waters of these rivers is ten times higher than the permissible concentration norm [5].

Figure 1 shows a map of mining facilities operating near the border regions of Armenia with Azerbaijan, Figure 2 shows images of liquid waste being discharged into the Kharchevan River (Agarak), and Figure 3 shows images of the discharge of hazardous mining waste from the Amulsar gold mine into the Vokchi River.

The demand for gold in our republic is increasing sharply. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct research and appropriate assessments in the areas of our country with gold reserves. In this sense, the Soyudlu (Zod) ore deposit, one of the main gold deposits in Eastern Zangezur, located on the border with Armenia, is of particular importance [5].

The Soyudlu (Zod) deposit was discovered in 1950 on the border of the Kalbajar and Basarkechar regions on the Azerbaijani side and the Armenian side. Although most of the deposit is located in Azerbaijan, control of the deposit was transferred to the Geological Department of Armenia by order of the Ministry of Geology during the USSR. The exploitation of the deposit began in 1976 and was carried out for commercial purposes. In 1976-1991, 28.5 tons of gold were extracted

from this deposit. In 1992, work on this deposit was suspended due to the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict.

However, on August 21, 1997, the Azerbaijani government included it in the first long-term international “gold contract” signed with RV Investment Company.

Figure 1. Mining facilities operating near the border regions of Armenia with Azerbaijan

Figure 2. Images of liquid waste discharge into the Kharchevan River, Agarak

Figure 3. Toxic mine waste discharged into the Voxchi River from the Amulsar gold mine

According to the Production Sharing Agreement (PSA) signed in 1997 between the Government of Azerbaijan and the London Stock Exchange (LSE), they stated that they would promptly inform the market about their plans for ore deposits located in the currently accessible regions of Azerbaijan. It should be noted that the agreement signed with RV Investment also included the Vejnalı gold deposit in the Zangilan region and the Qizilbulag gold deposit in the Aghdara

region. However, the Soyudlu gold deposit is considered one of the most valuable deposits due to its low content of impurities. Thus, the processing process is not only simple, but also much cheaper [1,10].

Figure 4 shows a general view of the Soyudlu (Zod) Gold Deposit, Figure 5 a) shows the location of the Soyudlu (Zod) Gold Deposit on the general map of Azerbaijan, and Figure 5 b) shows a separate large-scale map of that gold deposit.

Figure 4. General view of the Soyudlu (Zod) gold deposit

Studies have shown that the I, II, III Demirchidamı, Gonur, I, II Shargi Gunashli and Söyüdü gold ores have been discovered mainly in the eastern part of the Soyüdü (Zod) gold deposit. However, industrial-scale

gold reserves have been determined mainly in the Shargi Gunashli part, where the gold content is 3.1-11.1 g/t [10].

a)

b)

Figure 5. Location of the Soyudlu (Zod) Gold Deposit on the map of the Republic of Azerbaijan:

a) Location on the general map of Azerbaijan; b) Separate large-scale map

In recent years, a number of organizations engaged in ecology have noted a significant increase in the level of environmental pollution as a result of the processes occurring during the increase in gold mining. According to experts, during the extraction of gold, riverbeds are deformed, that is, before the gold layers are extracted, the riverbed is changed through special channels, and then the construction of dams and separate reservoirs begins so that the water can be reused. As a result, river waters can be discharged in appropriate directions, which creates conditions for the release of a significant amount of clay, chemicals, heavy metals and other toxic substances into the environment through these waters. All this ultimately leads to the

death of valuable fish species living in polluted water bodies, disruption of the river ecosystem, change of natural river beds and disruption of the ecosystem of coastal areas. Sometimes, it is even accompanied by flooding of surrounding areas and settlements and the destruction of forests. In large areas of the river network, the valleys created by the rivers are transformed into technogenic landscapes, which ultimately leads to the loss of many important ecosystem functions [10].

The rivers flowing through the Soyudlu (Zod) gold deposit include the Nakhchikhanchay, Tartarchay, Soyudluchay, etc. However, the largest of them is considered to be the Tartarchay, which is 205 km long and has a watershed area of 2,651 km² [10].

Table 1

Name of heavy metal	Permissible concentration, mg/l
Cadmium	0,002
Copper	2,0
Arsenic	0,04
Nickel	0,1
Hydrargyrum	0,0007
Lead	0,03
Zinc	6,0
Chromium	0,9
Cobalt	0,2

The most water-rich tributary of the Kura River within Azerbaijan is the Tertachay. The river is formed from springs flowing from the confluence of the Alaköz, Mikhtoken and Gongur ranges (3121 m). From the left are the Aghdabanchay (length 18 km), Levchay (length 37 km), and from the right is the Turagaychay (length 35 km). 29% of the river's water is formed by snow, 16% by rain, and 58% by groundwater. Due to the intensive melting of snow, floods occur in the river in the spring-summer months. At this time, the total flow is 66-75% of the annual indicator. In August-September, the water content in the rivers decreases. In October-November, rains again cause small floods in the river [12].

However, during gold mining, a number of toxic pollutants (mercury, cyanide) are discharged into the

Tartar River, as well as the washing of rocks and dust in water bodies, increased turbidity, etc., which negatively affect water resources and pose a threat to human health. In addition, a large amount of water is required for the development of the mining industry, and when water from working water sources is used for this purpose, it causes water shortages. Table 2 shows the concentrations of heavy metals discharged from the Soyudlu (Zod) gold deposit into the Tartar River in different months of the year. As can be seen from Table 2, the amount of Mercury and Cyanide, which are the most dangerous among heavy metals, discharged into the Tartar River in the autumn season is much higher than in the summer (June and July) months and is a thousand times higher than the permissible concentration limit [10].

Table 2

Months	Heavy metal salts, mg/l			
	Lead	Cadmium	Hydrargyrum	Cyanide
June	1,06	0,018	5,45	12,0
July	1,02	0,017	5,89	13,6
August	1,08	0,021	8,07	15,91
September	1,02	0,010	8,45	16,23
Average	1,05±0,02	0,019±0,002	6,95±0,77	14,26±1,04

The above can be clearly seen from the comparison of the data in Table 1 and Table 2. Thus, from the comparison of these two tables, it is clear that the amount of mercury, the most dangerous metal in the hazardous waste discharged into the Tartar River, is $5.45: 0.0007 = 7786$ times higher than the permissible concentration norm in July, when it is the lowest, and $8.45: 0.0007 = 12071$ times higher in September, when it is the highest. This makes the use of that water for any purpose completely impossible and extremely dangerous, even fatal in a short time.

Over the past 40 years, mercury has been used in artisanal and small-scale gold mining in over 50 countries. Mercury vapors are highly toxic to the respiratory tract and can cause serious health problems. Wastewater from mercury-based gold processing is typically discharged into rivers, waterways, water bodies, fish ponds, or rice fields, resulting in significant mercury emissions. For this reason, the most widely used and safest method for extracting gold from low-

grade ores is the cyanidation of gold to a water-soluble complex. This is known as the MacArthur-Forest process. Although cyanide solutions are primarily used in mining for gold extraction, they also react with other metals such as Na, Cu, Zn, and Co [12,4].

A very weak solution of sodium cyanide is used to dissolve and extract gold from the ore. This process was proposed in Scotland in 1887, but its first industrial use was recorded in 1889 at the Karangahake mine, a gold mining operation by Crown Mines in New Zealand. The cyanidation method is considered a safer alternative to the main compound previously used in gold extraction. Cyanidation is now the main technology for gold extraction, although in some countries small-scale and artisanal gold miners still use mercury. In many countries, more than 90% of the total gold mined (about 80 tons) uses cyanide. The normal concentration of sodium cyanide in the working solution is 0.01% to 0.05%. Miners try to use the lowest possible concentration of this solution, taking into account the factors such

as less damage to the environment, as well as achieving high safety and economic efficiency. Cyanidation is usually carried out in parallel with various physical enrichment processes (milling, gravity or crushing). To

prevent the conversion of cyanide ions to toxic cyanide gas, the pH of the final solution is raised by adding lime or other alkali. The gold is then concentrated, separated, and melted into ingots [4].

Figure 6. The section of the Tartarchay River passing near the Soyudlu (Zod) gold mine

Cyanide is also highly toxic. It is strictly regulated by the relevant authorities around the world. When ingested, cyanide inhibits oxygen absorption, causing suffocation and, if not treated promptly, even death. However, both humans and animals can quickly neutralize non-lethal amounts of the substance without any harmful effects. Many people can tolerate the toxic effects of cyanide in small doses. Some of the long-term negative effects of cyanide on human health include thyroid enlargement and dysfunction [3].

In fact, despite its high toxicity to humans, no fatal cases of cyanide poisoning have been recorded in any mining company in the past 100 years. This means that the danger of cyanide to humans can be eliminated by minimizing the risk of working with this chemical. Therefore, this process is controlled in production [6].

Despite the widespread use of cyanide by artisanal miners, the low contamination of waste material, and the existence of safe work practices, when mercury or other hazardous substances enter water sources, including mountain rivers, in this type of mining they cause the death of all types of living organisms living in water. The issues of accidental cyanide and mercury compounds entering the environment, including water sources, have been thoroughly investigated in countries around the world, and numerous reforms have been carried out in the mining industry to prevent similar situations from arising in the future. One such innovation was the introduction of the International Cyanide Management Code. The evaporation that occurs when cyanide compounds are discharged into water resources has a very serious negative impact on other natural processes. However, in such waters, microorganisms and plankton populations recover within a few days. For example: As a result of the earthquake that occurred in Japan in 1981, a large amount of cyanide from a gold mine entered the river. Although the chemical leak killed all living organisms, the occurrence of this process was detected only for three days. Within a month, flora began to grow again on the rocks above the water,

and within six to seven months, fish, algae, and invertebrate populations had recovered. Despite the continuous discharge of cyanide-containing industrial waste from a gold mine between 1974 and 1976, no traces of the chemical were found in the water and silt of Yellowknife Bay in the Northwest Territories of Canada [7].

Legal Framework for Cyanide Management in Gold Mines

The legislative bodies of many countries around the world, including Canada and Australia, recommend minimizing the use of cyanide, developing methods for protecting surface and groundwater, creating systems to reduce cyanide levels in wastewater, and preventing leaks, requiring the Code to be implemented [2,9].

In our country, cyanide and its compounds are considered potentially hazardous chemicals. As stipulated in the legislation, the relevant state authorities require that its transportation and processing be carried out in special containers, using certified equipment, and by trained personnel. The release of cyanides into the environment in the mining industry is regulated by legislation through the issuance of permits and licenses.

In addition, the maximum concentration of cyanide in the wastewater of the mining industry should be below 1 mg/L. The concentration of cyanide is measured in water samples. Studies show that these harmful substances enter water systems through human activity. Its chemical nature makes it toxic, especially in its organic form, posing a threat to human health and the environment. The mining industry will continue to develop alternative technologies and greatly improve chemical processing methods so that cyanide can be used relatively safely in the future.

Alternative chemicals for gold extraction should be investigated and found to have the same or even less harmful effects on the environment. However, current research suggests that cyanide-lime systems are the safest method of chemical gold extraction in terms of potential harmful effects on the environment and personnel. Research indicates that these harmful substances

enter water systems through human activities. Their chemical nature makes them toxic, especially in organic form, which poses a threat to human health and the environment. Although cyanide can currently be used relatively safely, the mining industry will continue to conduct research into alternative technologies and improve chemical processing methods.

Conclusion

1. As a result of the research, it became clear that the Soyudlu (Zod) gold deposit is considered one of the most valuable deposits due to the small amount of impurities in its composition. Thus, the processing process is not only simple, but also much cheaper. I, II, III Demirchidamy, Gonur, I, II Shargi Gunashli and Soyudlu gold ores were discovered mainly in the eastern part of this gold deposit. However, industrial-scale gold reserves were determined mainly in the Shargi Gunashli part, where the gold content is 3.1-11.1 g/t.

2. It became clear that during gold extraction, deformation of river beds occurs, that is, before extracting gold layers, the river bed is changed through special channels, and then the construction of dams and separate reservoirs begins so that water can be reused. As a result, river waters are discharged in the appropriate directions, which leads to the release of a significant amount of clay, chemicals, heavy metals and other toxic substances into the environment through these waters. All this ultimately leads to the death of living creatures living in polluted water bodies, including valuable fish species, the disruption of the river ecosystem and the overflow of natural river beds from their channels, causing natural disasters. In large areas of the river network, the valleys created by rivers are transformed into man-made landscapes and lead to the loss of many important ecosystem functions.

3. Water samples taken from the Tartarchay River were analyzed and it was found that the amount of mercury, the most dangerous metal in the harmful waste discharged into the Tartarcha River, was 5.45: 0.0007 = 7786 times higher than the permissible concentration in June, when it was the lowest, and 8.45: 0.0007 = 12071 times higher in September, when it was the highest. This makes the use of that water for any purpose completely impossible and extremely dangerous, even deadly in a short time.

4. From a comparative analysis of existing methods, it becomes clear that the most widespread and safest method for extracting gold from low-grade ores is cyanidation of gold by converting it into a water-soluble complex compound, which is known as the MacArthur-Forest process. Although cyanide solutions are primarily used in mining for gold extraction, they react with other metals such as Na, Cu, Zn, Co. Therefore, cyanidation has now become the main technology for gold extraction, although in some countries small-scale and artisanal gold miners still use mercury. In many countries, more than 90% of the total gold extracted (about 80 tons) is cyanide. The normal concentration of sodium cyanide in the working solution is 0.01% - 0.05%.

5. To prevent the conversion of cyanide ions into toxic cyanide gas, HCN, the pH of the final solution is increased by adding lime or other alkali. Only then is the gold concentrated, separated and melted into ingots. Long-term studies have shown that, in fact, despite its high toxicity to humans, no fatal cases of cyanide poisoning have been recorded in any of the mining companies over the past 100 years.

6. In Azerbaijan, cyanide and its compounds are considered potentially dangerous chemicals. Therefore, the relevant state authorities require that its transportation and processing be carried out by trained personnel using special containers, certified equipment, as specified in the legislation. The release of cyanides into the environment in the mining industry is regulated by legislation through the issuance of permits and licenses.

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